

THE IMPORTANCE OF NEW NORMS IN THE LABOR LEGISLATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the importance of new norms in the labour legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Labor Code, articles, new norms, duties, rights.

The newly revised Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on October 28, 2022 and entered into force on April 28, 2023. This Code consists of 2 parts - "General" and "Special" parts, 7 sections, 34 chapters and 581 articles. The articles of the new edition of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan are twice as many as the articles of the old Labor Code, that is, there were 294 articles in the old Labor Code.

Changes have been made to the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition, which serve the interests of employers and employees.

The Labor Code is a systematized set of labor laws. It is a legal document on labor. Labor relations of individuals working under labor contracts (contracts) in enterprises, institutions and organizations of all forms of ownership, as well as at the discretion of some citizens, are regulated by labor laws and other legal documents. In practice, other normative documents, in some cases the conventions of the International Labor Organization and the rules of international agreements are used to regulate labor relations. The Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was developed in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and international legal norms and standards.

The Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on December 21, 1995 and implemented from April 1, 1996. Part 2: general and special part, consists of 16 chapters and 294 articles. The general part describes the general rules of labor legislation, state administration in the field of labor, scope of application of labor

legislation, subjects of labor relations, their rights and duties, representation of employees and employers, collective agreements and agreements. A special part of the Labor Code is employment; employment contract (contract); working hours; rest time; payment of wages; guarantee payments and compensation payments; labor institution; material responsibility of the parties to the labor contract; labor protection; additional guarantees and benefits given to certain categories of employees; labor disputes; includes issues of state social insurance.

The main task of the Labor Code is to ensure the effective operation of the labor market, fair and safe working conditions, the protection of the labor rights and health of employees, the growth of labor productivity, the improvement of the quality of work, and on this basis, the material well-being of all the population, taking into account the interests of employees, employers, and the state. and contribute to the rise of the cultural standard of living.

Article 113 of the 2021 Labor Code has been amended. According to it, if the employee (if there is no contraindication) refuses to be vaccinated when there is a threat of quarantine and infectious diseases, the employer has the right not to employ the employee.

According to Article 96 of the newly revised Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, graduates of "Mehribonlik" houses are included in the category of additional guarantees in the field of employment of needy categories of the population. In the newly revised Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the term of the fixed-term employment contract has been shortened, that is, the part about the possibility of concluding a specific job for the time of performance has been removed from five years to three years. In the newly revised Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the grounds for terminating the employment contract have increased from 6 to 11 parts. In particular, the part at the initiative of one of the parties was divided into two separate parts at the initiative of an individual employee and at the initiative of the employer, the following parts were added:

- refusal of the employee to continue working under new working conditions;

- refusal of the employee to move to another place to work with the employer.

Article 228 of the new version of the Labor Code includes three more categories of employees - that is, women - before pregnancy and maternity leave. or after; to an employee who is using childcare leave before or after this leave; The persons awarded with the "Honorary Donor of the Republic of Uzbekistan" badge are included.

Another innovation included in the Labor Code in the new version is the procedure for remote work, permanent and temporary remote work, transition to temporary remote work at the initiative of the employer, mixed mode of remote work, about remote work employment contract, formalization of the acceptance and transfer of an employee to remote work, the category of employees who have the priority right to temporarily switch to remote work or transfer to remote work, specific features of the organization of their work, the employer and cooperation of the employee, the procedure for paying the employee's working time and labor, annual leave and the procedure for terminating the employment contract. The working order, duration of working hours, keeping records of working hours, work and rest regime during work, overtime work, granting annual vacation, and also the procedures for sending employees on business trips are included separately. There were no such changes in the current Labor Code. The reason for introducing remote work procedure into the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was the pandemic in our Republic.

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